

DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS-AS THE BASIS OF CREATIVE ABILITY

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Annotation: The article deals with the concept of creativity and features of its manifestation in the student age. The article describes the main active teaching methods and reveals their potential in terms of developing students' creativity. We also present data from an experimental study that shows the possibility of using active methods to develop certain parameters of creativity.

Keywords: creativity, ability, interactive methods, technology, pedagogical and psychological characteristics, criteria, levels, factors, stages, technological stages, results.

Critical thinking is one of the main skills of the 21st century, it allows you to analyze data, draw conclusions and make decisions based on analysis, as well as allow a person to form his own opinion and defend his own position. In the modern world, we are surrounded by information, they are obtained from various sources, and they need to be revised and checked for authenticity. Thanks to critical thinking, we see inconsistencies and contradictions, we can filter out misinformation and distinguish facts from their interpretation.

Training learners in critical thinking in the educational process is currently one of the urgent tasks of modern education. Faced with new information, it is necessary for students to independently evaluate it, look at it from different points of view, be able to draw conclusions about the possibility of using it in the path of their needs and goals. To grow up to be a true critical-minded person, it is essential that students think creatively and test themselves and acquire the skills and qualifications associated with it.[1]

Critical thinking is a system of judgments that are used from a critical point of view to analyze things and phenomena with the formation of reasonable conclusions and allow for reasonable assessment, interpretation, as well as the

correct application of results to situations and problems. [2]. In general, critical thinking refers to thinking at a higher level than subcritical thinking. Critical thinking is the ability of a person to doubt incoming information, including their own beliefs. There is an opinion that the transition to the level of critical thinking in a particular community is a prerequisite for the beginning of the development of civilization of this society[2].

The term "critical thinking" has long been used in educational environments, and different educators understand it differently. For most teachers and Methodists, critical thinking means "high - order" thinking-in this sense, it stands at the last Supreme step of learning abilities according to the Benjamin Blumm system. It is also considered to be a process that occurs simultaneously at several levels of active and interactive cognition. The owner of critical opinion is less influenced by tricks, being free from various dangers, since he has his own system of personal views. Critical thinking develops skills in communication and group work. Critical thinking gives enthusiasm to the educational process, turns training into joy for the teacher and student. For the emergence of critical thinking, there must be:

- emergence of a specific point of view in the student;
- skill to justify the advantage of one thought to another;
- skill in solving complex problems;
- argument by argument;
- the skill of working together to develop a single idea;
- to understand how life experience affects views and visions.[3]

Let's see clear ways that lead to critical thinking. However, there is a certain set of teaching conditions with which it is possible to educate critical thinkers. In particular, the following conditions are necessary:

1. Giving time and opportunity to gain critical thinking experience.
2. Give students the opportunity to think.
3. Acceptance of various ideas and opinions.
4. To allow active participation of students in the educational process.
5. To convince students that no one will laugh at them.
6. To convince every student that he is capable of critical reflection.
7. Appreciate the emergence of critical thinking.

Secondly, information is not the result of critical thinking, but its beginning. Knowledge is considered a motive that motivates a person to think critically. It is also sometimes said that "it is difficult to think with an empty head." To create a complex idea, it is necessary to process a lot of "raw materials"- evidence, ideas,

texts, theories, data, concepts.[4] Thirdly, critical thinking begins by identifying the problem in which the question needs to be posed and solved. Humanity is curious in its nature. We want to know the essence of the fact that any novelty is Caesar. Seeing some kind of historical monument, we have a desire to get inside it. Curiosity is an indispensable property of any living being. It is determined by his search for answers to questions arising from his personal interests and needs. Fourth, critical thinking seeks convincing evidence. A critical thinker will find his own personal solution to the problem and strengthen this decision with reasonable, reasonable arguments. He also acknowledges that there may be other decisions, but tries to prove that the decision he chooses is the most logical and rational in relation to others. Fifth, critical thinking is also considered a social phenomenon (each person is a social organism).[5]

Any thought is sharpened only if it is shared with others. When we debate, read, participate in the discussion, object, exchange ideas with others, we clarify our point of view and deepen it. Therefore, educators working in the direction of critical thinking strive to use different forms of work in pairs or groups in their training, to effectively use debate and discussion in this, and to use different manifestations of the demonstration of students' written work. In conclusion, different opinions develop as the group evolves into a student partnership society.[6] Students are active, and the teacher is considered a partner. Students take an active O'cuw pose. All this leads to a change in personality, which is a condition for having solid knowledge.

Literature used

1. [«Критическое мышление: отчёт об экспертном консенсусе в отношении образовательного оценивания и обучения»](#) // Dr. Peter A. Facione (Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences, Santa Clara University), Перевод с английского [Е. Н. Волковой](#). 2019-254 с.
2. Турчин В. Ф. «Феномен науки» [Wayback Machine](#) // Совершенство, 2013
3. Дьюи Джорж. [Психология и педагогика](#) / Пер. с англ. Н. М. Никольской. — М.: Совершенство, 2019 — 208 с.
4. В.Ляудис. Формирование учебной деятельности студентов, - М.: Издательство МГУ, 1989
5. Rakhmonova Dilnurakhon Saidovna. Pedagogical creativity as a factor of student development. International Scientific Research journal (WoS). ISSN:2776-0979 (Volume 2, Issue 5, May, 2021)
6. Rakhmonova Dilnura Saidovna Tirishga systematic approach to the development of students' creative abilities. "Berlin Studies" – Transnational journal of science and humanities. Vol. 1 No. 15. Pedagogical sciences (2021): <http://berlinstudies.de/>